

Development of a Visual Tool for Data Management in Recycling Cooperatives: A User-Centered Approach

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Abstract

The Data Management System is essential for increasing operational efficiency by collecting and visualizing data to support informed decision-making by waste pickers. This article evaluates a visual tool for the Data Management System application; a platform designed for recyclable material cooperatives in the Federal District. The project was developed within the Production Project 5 course, using project-based learning (PBL). In this approach, students collaborate to solve real-world problems through research, requirements gathering, prototyping, and validation with stakeholders (in this case, a recycling cooperative), promoting practical and interdisciplinary learning. The app will be developed by software engineering students as part of the Egalitarian project, under the ERASMUS+ program funded by the European Union. The research follows a qualitative, exploratory, and applied approach, focusing on three key aspects. First, it identifies high-level requirements for the web app's functionalities and prioritizes them using the Kano Model. Next, it involves designing the interface screens for the app's modules in Figma, ensuring an intuitive and user-friendly experience. Finally, an interactive and functional dashboard is developed and validated by waste pickers, who will be the app's primary users. The concept was tested at the Recicla Mais Brasil cooperative in the Federal District. The study aims to develop a fully functional system that enables the visualization of key performance indicators, improving operational control and facilitating strategic decision-making for the recycling cooperative.

Keywords: Egalitarian Project, Data Management System, Waste Pickers, Requirements Gathering, Active Learning.

1 Introduction

In the era of technology and with the availability of data present in today's society, information has become a valuable resource for organizations. According to Sarioguz and Miser (2023), the increasing dependence on data is driven by the understanding that when efficiently understood, they can provide valuable insights.

According to Michalski Filho, Resende, and Gaia (2010), recycling cooperatives face significant challenges related to operational efficiency and information management, often due to the lack of integrated data management systems. The absence of suitable tools to collect, organize, and analyse data negatively impacts these institutions' ability to monitor operations and make evidence-based decisions.

Data play a fundamental role in optimizing operational activities to increase the income of collectors (Ferreira, Kintschner & Sugahara, 2022). The managerial difficulties present in this scenario are evidenced by the lack of education among collectors, as more than 80 percent of collectors do not receive formal education beyond primary school, according to Bouvier (2021). Coupled with the lack of instruction, the use of precarious and manual systems fosters distrust and conflict among cooperatives, as noted by Barros and Moura (2022).

The Data Management System (DMS) is a project being developed under the Egalitarian project, which is part of the Erasmus+ Program, funded by the European Union. The Egalitarian project focuses on developing international projects carried out by students under the supervision of professors from different universities, aimed at proposing improvements to the solid waste management system in Brazil, emphasizing recyclable

material collectors in the Federal District. The solutions proposed by the students must align with sustainability and digital technologies, addressing the growing demand for technological tools that aim to increase the competitiveness and sustainability of cooperatives, aligning with environmental and economic needs.

The DMS project emerged in response to a cooperative's demand to visualize accessible data for all collaborators regarding the productivity of collectors, daily production by material type, to facilitate cooperative management and provide greater transparency to members. Considering this context, this article aims to detail the DMS system that was conceived by the students, its requirements and functionalities, prototypes, and dashboards.

2 Theoretical Framework

Recycling cooperatives play a fundamental role in solid waste management, promoting environmental sustainability and social inclusion. However, they face challenges related to operational efficiency and information fragmentation. Ferreira et al. (2022), Barros and Moura (2022) indicate that the adoption of integrated management systems and information technologies can optimize processes, improve decision-making, and increase the competitiveness of these organizations. This theoretical framework explores the importance of these systems, addressing their application in areas such as production, inventory, reverse logistics, and sustainability.

2.1 Integrated Management

Recycling cooperatives play a fundamental role in waste management, promoting environmental sustainability and social inclusion. However, as noted by Michalski Filho, Resende, and Gaia (2010), these organizations face challenges in operational efficiency and information management. The lack of integrated data management systems leads to fragmented processes and ineffective decision-making, affecting competitiveness and sustainability. In this context, the adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) emerges as a promising solution to optimize operations and improve the strategic management of recycling cooperatives, according to Barros and Moura (2022). This theoretical framework examines the importance of data management systems in cooperatives, addressing their application in production, inventory, reverse logistics, and sustainability.

Barros and Moura (2022) emphasize that systemic management is essential for the success of waste picker cooperatives. Organizational performance is linked to the management of information technology (IT) and information systems (IS), which requires proper alignment between organizational systems and the IT/IS sector. Henderson and Venkatraman (1993) argued that the economic performance of an organization could be improved by aligning IT strategy with business strategy, as well as aligning infrastructure and organizational processes with IS structures.

2.2 Production and Inventory Management in Recycling Cooperatives

Ferreira et al. (2022) highlight that production and inventory management is one of the main challenges faced by recycling cooperatives, especially due to the lack of tools that allow efficient monitoring of material flow. In this context, the use of technologies based on agile methods, such as Scrum, facilitates the development of customized systems that are adaptable to the specific needs of cooperatives. These solutions enable organizations to have greater control over the materials collected, stored, and reused, minimizing losses and maximizing operational efficiency.

In addition, the system proposed by Ferreira et al. (2022) organizes data into modules, covering everything from sorting control to contract management with clients, integrating all stages of the production process. This

not only improves efficiency but also promotes greater transparency in operations, creating trust among members and stakeholders. By adopting this approach, cooperatives can better meet market demands and position themselves as strategic partners in the sector, strengthening their financial and operational sustainability.

2.3 Requirement Elicitation

Requirements elicitation is a crucial step in system development, as it directly influences the success or failure of a project. According to Sommerville (2011), this activity seeks to identify, document, and validate the needs of stakeholders, ensuring that the final system meets the expectations and proposed objectives. Among the techniques used are interviews, brainstorming, and analyses that help capture relevant information and reduce gaps among those involved. Studies such as those by Wieggers and Beatty (2013) highlight that the application of well-defined techniques improves communication among stakeholders and increases clarity regarding functional and non-functional requirements. Furthermore, the choice of the best technique should consider factors such as the organizational context, project complexity, and available tools. Inadequate requirements elicitation is one of the main causes of rework and project failures in software development, as noted by Glass (2005), reinforcing the need for systematic and collaborative approaches in this phase.

2.4 Usability Principles in Web Interfaces

Usability is one of the fundamental pillars for the success of web interfaces, directly affecting the user experience and the effectiveness of the system. According to Nielsen (1994), a usable interface must be efficient, intuitive, and pleasant, facilitating the user's interaction with the system. Principles such as consistency, immediate feedback, simplicity, and accessibility are widely discussed in the literature and have been applied in various contexts, as reported by Lazar, Feng, and Hochheiser (2017). Research indicates that interfaces that follow good usability practices have higher user retention rates and lower abandonment rates, especially in competitive environments such as e-commerce (Garrett, 2011).

Furthermore, conducting usability tests throughout the development process is essential to identify problems and refine the interface, ensuring a satisfactory experience for different user profiles. These principles become even more relevant as the diversity of devices and usage contexts increases, requiring adaptable and user-centered solutions.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research classification

The article can be classified in terms of purpose as descriptive, as it aims to detail the development and implementation of a system to optimize the management of cooperatives without establishing causal relationships (Gil, 2008). In terms of approach, the research is qualitative, as there is a theoretical review and validation with experts (Creswell, 2010). It is applied research, with the aim of solving a practical and concrete problem, collecting real data and seeking a practical solution to the cooperative's issue, focusing on optimizing management (Lakatos & Marconi, 2017), (Yin, 2015).

3.2 Research structure

The research was structured in 4 stages to report the initial design of the Data Management System.

Figure 1. Stages of the research, Developed by the authors (2025)

In the first stage, user profiles were developed, requirements were defined and refined based on the KANO matrix, and the initial data architecture was created following a technical visit to the Recicla Mais Brasil cooperative in the Federal District. In the second stage, the focus was directed towards the development of non-functional prototypes in Figma. In the third stage, another visit to the cooperative was made to validate the indicators and visualization formats. Potential users, cooperative directors, and 4 recyclers were interviewed to validate the information. And finally, in the fourth stage, the interactive dashboard was consolidated, demonstrating the indicators of the cooperative's operations.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Cooperative Structure and Organization

To carry out an initial diagnosis of the model cooperative, a technical visit was conducted to understand the organizational structure, the processes carried out, and the data collected in the organization. The organizational structure of the cooperative is divided into two main functions: administrative and operational. The administrative board, made up of waste pickers, plays a strategic and managerial role, being responsible for articulating improvements with other organizations and with the government, selling the sorted material, controlling finances, and supervising operations. The operational part consists of 50 waste pickers who work on the cooperative's production line. This group performs daily activities such as receiving, sorting, and organizing the received material.

The main processes present in the cooperative are sorting, weighing, selling the received material, and paying the members. In the sorting process, the content is separated according to the type and color of the material. In weighing, each waste picker is responsible for weighing the material they handle on that day, while one of the waste pickers from the administrative board manually records the observed weight. Finally, the sale of the material is carried out later by the administration. The data observed in these activities includes: the weight of the material sorted by each waste picker daily, the number of bags of sorted material per day, the selling price of each material, and the payment value for each member. Thus, with the aim of ensuring transparency between the two roles, the DMS system is designed for a Web version, intended for the administrative board, and an app version, proposed for the waste pickers.

4.2 Requirements

The Kano matrix is a tool for classifying and prioritizing product or service requirements based on their impact on customer satisfaction, shown in Figure 2. Developed by Noriaki Kano in the 1980s, it categorizes attributes into five groups: basic, performance, attractive, indifferent, and reverse. According to Sauerwein et al. (1996), this matrix helps development teams identify essential features, those that increase satisfaction proportionally, and those that can pleasantly surprise customers. Its main goal is to guide strategic decisions in product design and development, ensuring value delivery and alignment with target audience expectations.

Figure 2. Kano Matrix, Developed by the authors (2024)

Based on the Kano matrix, the requirements were classified and prioritized. Thus, the system requirements gathered, and the functionalities are described in Table 1.

Requirements	System Functionalities
Ability to apply filters for result visualization	Screen filters for: -Date (select time intervals), -Material type, -Waste picker. Data visualization section containing: -Bar chart showing total production by material type, -Line chart showing total production per day, - Line chart showing total production per waste picker.
An intuitive interface for selecting time periods from a predefined list, without manually entering date ranges	
An intuitive interface for selecting material types from a predefined list, without manually entering names	
An intuitive interface for selecting waste picker names from a predefined list, without manually entering names	
Only three response visualizations (outputs) to simplify result analysis	
Charts with thick, visible lines	
Charts with legends and contrasting colors	

Table 1. Requirements and functionalities of the DMS App, Developed by the authors (2024)

Thus, the prioritized functionalities demonstrate the initial characteristics of the system. The implementation of filters facilitates the visualization of individual data, which aids in decision-making. Additionally, the use of bar and line graphs combined with contrasting colors reinforces visual understanding.

4.3 Non-functional prototypes

An app screen prototype is a visual representation that simulates the design and functionality of app interfaces before full development. It can range from a simple paper sketch to an interactive digital mockup, allowing visualization of element placement, navigation flow, and user experience. According to Snyder (2003), prototypes help validate ideas, identify usability issues, and align expectations between stakeholders and the development team. Their purpose is to reduce rework, save resources, and ensure that the final product meets user needs and project goals.

The non-functional prototypes (Figures 3 and 4) were developed using Figma to simulate user interaction and navigation.

Figure 3. App Screen prototyped, Developed by the authors (2024)

Figure 4. Web Screen prototyped, Developed by the authors (2024)

The app prototype (Figure 3) showcases the mobile interface, highlighting the summary and notification screens to support quick and efficient user interaction. The web prototype (Figure 4) presents the desktop version, emphasizing usability and accessibility, and includes dashboards and analytics to illustrate key data in a clear and visually accessible format. Both were created to simulate the user journey and align with the intended user experience.

4.4 Validation with the cooperative

For the validation of the prototypes and indicators, a technical visit was conducted at the Recicla Mais Brasil cooperative in the Federal District. Three members of the cooperative's board participated, showed enthusiasm for the developed solution, and the desired functionalities were extracted, in addition to those raised. Based on suggestions from the collectors, the need for the development of a functionality to send general notices emerged to ensure efficient communication within the cooperative. The "Send Notice" screen allows users to select recipients, format the text, and schedule notifications, with a send button prominently displayed to facilitate use.

4.5 Dashboard

At the Recicla Mais Brasil cooperative, the scale used to collect the weight of sorted materials is not an automated process, therefore, there are no sensors or hardware implemented, as can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Digital scale used by the Recicla Mais Brasil Cooperative, Own authorship

The automation project for the scale is being developed by Brazilian students from the Production Engineering and Software Engineering courses, in partnership with Danish students from the Computer Science course. As the process is not yet automated and due to the lack of data recorded in an automated manner, it was necessary to create a spreadsheet with fictitious data, as shown in Figure 6.

Collection Date	Worker	Material Type	Recycled Weight	Sale Value (R\$)	Price per Kg (R\$/Kg)	Hours Worked	Reference Month
10/12/2024	João	Glass	36,85	86,23	2,34	3,18	October 2024
01/20/2024	Ana	Plastic	45,99	79,1	1,72	1,5	January 2024
10/02/2024	Maria	Glass	13,06	51,2	3,92	3,3	October 2024
08/04/2024	Ana	Steel Cans	19,29	61,73	3,2	3,48	August 2024
08/25/2024	Maria	Plastic	9,35	5,24	0,56	6,16	August 2024
01/18/2024	Ana	Paper	23,12	111,9	4,84	6,41	January 2024
11/11/2024	Carlos	Plastic	46,2	35,11	0,76	7,51	November 2024
08/26/2024	Carlos	Glass	15,72	51,56	3,28	5,19	August 2024
10/28/2024	Carlos	Aseptic Packaging	40,23	52,3	1,3	1,27	October 2024
08/13/2024	Carlos	Aseptic Packaging	22,86	74,75	3,27	2,38	August 2024
10/03/2024	Carlos	Metal Cans	14,35	49,65	3,46	5,81	October 2024
12/26/2024	Pedro	Aseptic Packaging	22,95	96,39	4,2	7,46	December 2024
10/06/2024	Maria	Metal Cans	49,49	238,54	4,82	3,01	October 2024
04/04/2024	Maria	Aseptic Packaging	31,94	108,92	3,41	3,3	April 2024
06/18/2024	Pedro	Plastic	11,94	17,67	1,48	4,23	June 2024
11/20/2024	Carlos	Metal Cans	9,33	28,83	3,09	6,2	November 2024
01/19/2024	Ana	Aseptic Packaging	26,91	58,13	2,16	6,46	January 2024
04/11/2024	Maria	Paper	46,17	133,89	2,9	7,65	April 2024
03/29/2024	Maria	Paper	14,79	19,52	1,32	4,35	March 2024
12/19/2024	Ana	Paper	27,63	44,21	1,6	6,02	December 2024
10/25/2024	Maria	Plastic	15,36	63,74	4,15	1,82	October 2024
05/23/2024	Ana	Metal Cans	25,55	37,81	1,48	4,09	May 2024
04/01/2024	João	Glass	39,98	145,53	3,64	1,15	April 2024
06/25/2024	Pedro	Metal Cans	23,03	14,28	0,62	6,81	June 2024
07/31/2024	João	Paper	27,17	26,9	0,99	7,62	July 2024
02/04/2024	Carlos	Steel Cans	19,61	21,37	1,09	6,44	February 2024
09/08/2024	Carlos	Plastic	22,69	65,35	2,88	1,62	September 2024
04/16/2024	Ana	Plastic	13,09	48,69	3,72	1,32	April 2024
08/23/2024	Maria	Aseptic Packaging	34,59	122,79	3,55	6,07	August 2024

Figure 6. Database, Developed by the authors (2025)

This data served as the basis for structuring the Dashboard, which is essential for the control and management of the cooperative, benefiting both the managers and the collectors.

The Dashboard (Figure 7) presents an intuitive and functional interface, prioritizing simplicity and efficiency in data analysis. It allows dynamic filtering based on three main criteria: time period, type of material, and name of the collector, using predefined lists to avoid manual data entry. The visualizations include a bar chart for total production by type of material and two-line charts highlighting daily production and by collector, with an accessible design and contrasting colors to facilitate interpretation.

Figure 7. Dashboard, Developed by the authors (2025)

The implementation of the Dashboard in the cooperative optimizes operational management and internal communication, providing a clear view of activities. Data filtering helps identify performance patterns and improvement opportunities, such as determining which materials have the highest production. The "Send Notice" screen speeds up communication about schedule changes and new goals, ensuring that everyone stays informed. In the context of cooperatives, the Dashboard and the integrated communication tools enhance control, transparency, and collaboration, contributing to more efficient management and the achievement of strategic objectives.

5 Conclusion

This study aimed to assist recycling cooperatives in developing an efficient plan for the collection, processing, and management of recyclable products, using integrated analysis and communication tools in Information Systems. Brazil presents a promising scenario for recycling but faces challenges in the integration of public policies and business initiatives. The development of a data management system with a dashboard module that displays operational production data and internal communication facilitates better resource management for production control, through the analysis of key indicators, as well as improvements in internal communication.

Limitations were observed throughout the research, such as the limited number of collectors for the validation of prototypes and the dashboard, the effectiveness of the process of evaluating information by the collectors, and resistance to change observed by the cooperative members. It is suggested as future work to develop strategies for engaging cooperative members and assess the effectiveness of implementing technologies to strengthen recycling cooperatives in the Federal District.

To ensure the continuity of the initiative, an interdisciplinary team of students and teachers is working to implement innovative technologies and encourage entrepreneurship among collectors of recyclable materials during the Egalitarian project.

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